

Sustainable recovery of astaxanthin from *Haematococcus pluvialis* using green natural deep eutectic solvents (NADES)

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Background/Problem

Astaxanthin is a high-value natural carotenoid with a growing market, but common extraction routes often rely on conventional solvents or supercritical CO₂ and multiple downstream steps (including dilution in edible oils for standardisation). There is a need for a simpler, scalable extraction approach that reduces toxicity concerns, processing steps, and energy use.

Practice Change

Replace conventional solvent/CO₂-based extraction with a NADES-based extraction using mid-chain fatty acid NADES, enabling direct recovery of astaxanthin into a non-toxic “green” solvent system that can be used as-is in formulations or further processed if a solvent-free product is required.

Evidence

Haematococcus pluvialis can accumulate astaxanthin at ~4–5% of dry biomass under stress conditions, making it a strong natural source. This approach uses novel green NADES to extract astaxanthin under mild, energy-efficient conditions and with reduced solvent quantities aligned with green chemistry principles. Unlike typical workflows, the extract can be directly incorporated into products due to NADES’ non-toxic nature, or the solvent can be recovered via polarity switching to support downstream flexibility and potential cost savings.

Setting/Participants

Ingredient manufacturers and processors in food, nutraceutical, pharmaceutical, or cosmetics value chains seeking greener extraction routes; R&I carried out at FINS, University of Novi Sad, Serbia.

Implementation Plan

Prepare the selected NADES on-site (as they are not commercially available), implement the extraction process using the NADES system, and choose the downstream route: (a) use the NADES extract directly in end products where permitted, or (b) apply polarity switching to separate/recover solvent for a solvent-free formulation. Build in quality control and standardisation to ensure batch-to-batch reproducibility.

Outcomes/Measures

Astaxanthin extraction performance (yield/concentration), solvent consumption, solvent recovery rate (if polarity switching is used), energy use, processing steps/time vs baseline methods, product compatibility (direct-use extracts), and techno-economic feasibility (including sensitivity to raw material price).

Conclusion

NADES-based astaxanthin recovery from *H. pluvialis* offers a promising simplified, scalable, and greener alternative to conventional extraction, potentially reducing processing complexity and improving sustainability, while key implementation needs include on-site NADES preparation, standardisation/QC, solvent recycling, and full techno-economic assessment for scale-up.

Astaxanthin projected

CAGR of 7.11 (2030)

Haematococcus pluvialis

accumulates **4-5%**
astaxanthin of its dry biomass

